

Substituted 12-Aminobenz/b/Acridines

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The synthesis of substituted 7-aminobenz/c/acridines as potential amoebicides has been reported by Elslager *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4699; 1958, **80**, 451) and by Short *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1958, **80**, 223). Chatterjee (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 856, 2067) reported the preparation of a few substituted 12-aminobenz/a/acridines and 7-aminobenz/c/acridines as potential amoebicides. The present communication deals with the preparation of some substituted 12-aminobenz/b/acridines for trial on *E. histolytica*.

The compounds were obtained by the action of 12-chlorobenz/b/acridine, prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid according to Bachman *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, **13**, 89), on the appropriate amine in phenol (Table I).

TABLE I

No.	Compound.	Formula.	M.P.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	12- <i>p</i> -Chloroanilinobenz/b/A	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ Cl	254°	77.69	77.96	3.80	4.23
2	12- <i>m</i> -Chloroanilinobenz/b/A	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ Cl	210°	78.10	77.96	4.20	4.23
3	12- <i>p</i> -Bromoanilinobenz/b/A	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ Br	260°	69.26	69.17	3.56	3.76
4	12- <i>m</i> -Bromoanilinobenz/b/A	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ Br	203°	69.10	69.17	3.43	3.76
5	12- <i>p</i> -Anisidinobenz/b/A	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ ON ₂	213°	82.44	82.29	4.78	5.14
6	12- <i>p</i> -Toluidinobenz/b/A	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂	210°	86.33	86.23	5.00	5.39
7	12- <i>m</i> -Toluidinobenz/b/A	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂	202°	85.99	86.23	4.92	5.39
8	12-Anilinobenz/b/A	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂	228°	85.94	86.25	4.76	5.00
9	12-(8'-Quinoly) aminobenz/b/A	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ N ₃	278°	84.44	84.10	4.58	4.58
10	12-(6'-Chloro-8'-quinoly)-aminobenz/b/A	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ Cl	294°	77.14	76.94	3.69	3.95
11	12-(2'-Phenoxyethyl)-aminobenz/b/A-S	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ ON ₂ , C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	205°	76.75	76.49	4.91	5.18
12	12-(3'-Phenoxypropyl)-aminobenz/b/A-S	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ ON ₂ , C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	211°	76.94	76.74	5.05	5.43
13	12-(1'-Naphthyl)-aminobenz/b/A-S	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ , C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	212°	80.25	80.31	4.44	4.72
14	12-(2'-Naphthyl)-aminobenz/b/A-S	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ , C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	232°	80.11	80.31	4.69	4.72

N.B.—A stands for acridine and S for salicylate.

General Method of Preparation.—12-Chlorobenz/b/acridine (0.005*M*) was dissolved in freshly distilled phenol (15c.c.) by heating on steam and a slight excess of the appropriate amine added. The mixture was kept at 120° for 2 hours and then poured into an excess of a solution of KOH in water. The base was filtered, washed with water, dried, and purified by crystallisation from benzene, followed by a second crystallisation from 90% ethanol.

In the case of the compounds No. 11 to 14 (Table I), the bases are highly soluble in common solvents. These were extracted with ether and the extract treated with a solution of salicylic acid in ether. After keeping for a few hours, the salicylate was filtered, washed with ether, and crystallised from 90% ethanol.

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